

Numerical Study of Viscous Fluid Flow at the Inlet Section

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Abstract—This paper numerically investigates the nature of laminar flow at the inlet section of a flat pipe to analyze the hydrodynamic interaction between a viscous incompressible fluid flow and a stationary rigid cylinder located in the channel cross-section. Using the finite volume method with the solution of the full Navier–Stokes equations in dimensionless form, a detailed modeling of steady flows is performed at Reynolds numbers $Re = 10\text{--}200$, corresponding to the predominance of viscous forces over inertial ones. Particular attention is paid to the spatial evolution of the velocity field, the formation of boundary layers, and vortex structures at the inlet section, where the velocity profile has not yet reached a stationary parabolic distribution. The pressure and shear stress distributions on the cylinder surface are calculated, allowing us to quantify the components of the hydrodynamic forces: the drag force and the lift force acting on a particle depending on its transverse position.

Key words: Navier-Stokes, flat pipe, laminar flow, particle in flow, M-shaped profile.

I. INTRODUCTION

Theoretical and experimental studies of two-phase flow dynamics focus on the behavior of solid particles in liquid and gas flows [1–3]. Understanding the mechanisms of transport, sedimentation, and lateral displacement of particles is fundamental for applications in chemical engineering, biomedical devices, filtration, aerodynamics, and environmental systems.

One key aspect of this problem is determining the transverse (lift) forces acting on particles in non-uniform flows. Experimental observations by G. Segre and A. Zilberberg [4], which demonstrated the displacement of spherical particles in laminar flow in a pipe to a specific radial position (the so-called Segre-Zilberberg effect), became the catalyst for an entire line of research aimed at deriving analytical expressions for the lift force. These experiments demonstrated that even in the absence of gravity and electrostatic effects, particles experience a significant lateral force due to hydrodynamic velocity gradients. The first analytical expression for the lift force acting on a spherical particle in an unbounded linear flow was obtained by Saffman [5] in the context of an asymptotic analysis of the Navier–Stokes equations at low Reynolds numbers ($Re \ll 1$). His formula, proportional to the product of the flow vorticity and the velocity gradient, became the basis for subsequent work. However, as subsequent studies have shown, with increasing Reynolds numbers or in the presence of boundaries, this formula requires adjustment.

Many authors have attempted to expand and refine Saffman's model. In [6, 7], corrections were introduced to account for inertial effects and the nonlinearity of the velocity field, which allowed for increased prediction accuracy in the range of $Re \sim 1\text{--}10$. Asmolov [8] applied the method of matched asymptotic expansions to obtain an expression for the transverse force acting on a spherical particle in a laminar boundary layer and derived it through a multiple integral dependent

on the velocity profile and flow parameters. Subsequently, using Asmolov's corrections [8, 9], particle motion in Couette flow was investigated in [10], where the velocity gradient is linear but a rigid boundary is present, significantly affecting the vortex distribution.

In [11], the influence of both flow inertia and the proximity of a rigid boundary on the magnitude and direction of lift was systematically studied for the first time. It was shown that as a particle approaches a wall, the force can change sign—this phenomenon is important for modeling sedimentation in microchannels. In [12], a numerical Fourier decomposition method was used to analyze the effect of inertia on lift in a linear velocity field, enabling data to be obtained for $Re = 0.1-100$ and revealing the nonlinear dependence of the force on Reynolds number.

However, all of the above studies focused on spherical particles in unbounded or semi-infinite flows. In real systems—such as heat exchangers, filters, and microreactors—particles are often cylindrical, and the flow is confined by solid walls. In [13], a numerical study of two-dimensional unsteady flow past an infinite cylinder was performed using the Navier-Stokes equations in streamfunction-vortex variables, providing a detailed picture of the vortex structure and pressure distribution. However, this study did not consider lift as such, nor did it examine the effect of the cylinder's positioning in the channel.

The objective of this study is to numerically investigate the steady-state flow of a viscous incompressible fluid past a solid cylinder located at the inlet section of a flat pipe. Particular attention is paid to the formation of an M-shaped structure at the inlet section as a function of the Reynolds number; determining the magnitude and direction of the force acting on the cylinder; studying the dependence of this force on the cylinder's transverse position in the channel; and identifying the geometric parameters at which the lift force reaches a maximum or changes sign. The results of the work allow us not only to expand existing understanding of hydrodynamic forces to non-spherical particles, but also to create a basis for developing more accurate models of the sedimentation and transport of cylindrical particles in microchannels and porous media.

II. MATHEMATICAL AND NUMERICAL MODEL

A. Problem Statement

To study the flow of a viscous fluid at the inlet region in the presence of a single cylindrical particle with the cylinder axis perpendicular to the flow, we first consider the flow behavior without the particle. At the entrance to a channel, a uniform viscous flow exhibits an M-shaped longitudinal velocity profile in the initial cross-sections of the channel. The flow in the inlet region is particularly significant due to the flow's transformation into a Poiseuille profile before stabilization. The uniform inlet flow subsequently acquires a parabolic velocity distribution. Due to the no-slip boundary condition, the uniform flow at the inlet is deformed and is described as a two-dimensional problem.

The appearance of an M-shaped velocity profile in various processes has been encountered in the literature [14-19]. In [14-17], fluid flow in partially filled porous media was numerically studied at various positions within the porous medium. Numerical results showed that an M-shaped non-uniform flow is observed behind the porous layer.

Experimental studies by M.A. Goldshtik [18] revealed that measuring the gas flow velocity directly behind a granular layer revealed that it can be significantly greater in the near-wall region compared to the velocity in the channel center, i.e., an M-shaped velocity profile was observed behind the granular layer. Theoretical results for obtaining such types of velocity profiles are also reported in [19]. In this work, a velocity profile was obtained that confirms the experimental results of [18].

The formation of an M-shaped profile is observed not only behind the granular layer, but also during fluid movement in the inlet section of the pipe.

Thus, to obtain a flow pattern, the flow of a viscous fluid in a flat pipe is considered. The Cartesian coordinate system is arranged as follows: the Ox-axis is directed along the lower wall of the pipe, and the Oy-axis is perpendicular to it. To study the effect of a particle on the flow, we place it at any point in the region under consideration.

B. Mathematical Model

Assuming a two-dimensional flow for mathematical modeling, we use the Navier-Stokes system of equations [20].

The dimensionless form of the Navier-Stokes equations is:

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \Delta u, \quad u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \Delta v, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0. \quad (2)$$

System of equations (1)-(2) is considered in the domain $D: x \in [0, 5], y \in [0, 1]$, Re is the Reynolds number, ($\text{Re} = UH / \nu$, where U is the average velocity, H is the channel width, ν is the kinematic viscosity coefficient), u is the longitudinal velocity, v is the transverse velocity, p is the pressure, and Δ is the Laplace operator. To compare the results, three types of boundary conditions are considered. In all three variants, no-slip conditions are assumed at the rigid boundaries $u = 0, v = 0$. At the pipe outlet, the following conditions are used:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0.$$

In the first variant, a uniform flow is used at the inlet: $u = 1, v = 0, p = p_0$ without an internal cylinder to reveal the M-shaped velocity profile. The second variant applies to flow around a stationary cylinder; no-slip boundary conditions are imposed. In the third variant, the input flow is given by Poiseuille's law through an internal cylinder $u = 6y(1 - y), v = 0, p = p_0$.

C. Numerical Model

The SIMPLE algorithm, described in detail in [21, 22], is used to numerically solve the Navier-Stokes equations (1)-(2) with given boundary conditions. This algorithm is based on sequential correction of the velocity and pressure fields and ensures that the continuity condition is satisfied at each step of the iterative process.

Calculations are performed on a staggered non-uniform grid, which improves the stability and accuracy of calculations when solving viscous incompressible fluid flow problems. The main (pressure) grid is constructed such that its nodes are located directly on the cylinder surface; that is, a geometry-consistent computational grid is used [23]. This approach ensures a more accurate specification of boundary conditions on a solid surface and reduces the approximation error near the boundary.

Since significant velocity and pressure gradients, as well as intense flow deformation, are observed in the vicinity of the cylinder, a non-uniform grid with localized node concentrations near the surface is used. The total number of grid cells is 50×40 , which provides a compromise between solution accuracy and computational cost. When the cylinder's position changes, the grid is automatically rebuilt while maintaining the boundary-consistent principle, allowing for the correct accounting of the new configuration of the computational domain.

The cylinder's surface is discretized with sufficient detail: 20 nodes are identified along the circumference, ensuring an adequate description of the velocity and pressure distribution at the boundary. This partitioning allows for the correct accounting of the no-slip and no-flow boundary conditions.

After spatial discretization, the differential equations are transformed into a system of algebraic equations. The resulting system is solved using an iterative relaxation method until the specified convergence in velocity and pressure is achieved. The convergence criterion is the reduction of the equation residuals to a specified small value, which guarantees the stability and reliability of the resulting numerical solution.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Flow structure at the inlet section without considering the cylinder

As established above, a characteristic M-shaped longitudinal velocity profile is observed behind the porous layer, caused by the combined effects of viscosity, inertia, and hydrodynamic flow development. A similar phenomenon is also observed at the inlet section of a straight pipe during viscous incompressible flow—this is a classic example of the hydrodynamic inlet effect.

Figure 1(a) shows the longitudinal velocity profiles u for a Reynolds number of $Re = 10$ (for clarity, all velocity values are scaled by a factor of 0.2). In the immediate vicinity of the inlet section ($x \approx 0$), the profile has a pronounced M-shaped character: two local velocity maxima form near the channel walls, and a zone of low, nearly uniform velocity forms in the central region. This is due to the fact that at the inlet, the flow has not yet had time to adapt to no-slip conditions on the walls, and inertial forces, which predominate over viscous forces, "push" the fluid toward the periphery.

As the distance from the inlet increases ($x > 0.5$), the viscous forces gradually flatten the profile: local maxima near the walls weaken, and the central zone accelerates. At $x \approx 2$ (in units of the channel radius), the M-shaped profile completely disappears, and a parabolic profile, characteristic of developed laminar flow in a pipe (Poiseuille flow), forms.

With increasing Reynolds number (see Fig. 1b, $Re=200$), the length of the inlet section, where the M-shaped structure is maintained, increases significantly. This is due to the decreasing relative influence of viscous forces compared to inertial forces. The maximum velocity points, located symmetrically relative to the channel axis, slowly converge, not disappearing immediately but gradually "shifting" toward the center. Upon reaching a certain distance, these two maxima merge into a single central peak, after which the profile continues to evolve toward parabolicity.

Thus, the evolution of the velocity profile in the inlet section represents a dynamic transition from a nonequilibrium, inertial-dominated state to a viscous-controlled steady state. The M-shaped profile is an intermediate, transient state that does not exist in a developed flow but plays a key role in shaping the boundary layer structure and momentum distribution along the channel.

B. Drag and Lift Forces Acting on a Cylinder at the Pipe Inlet

As noted above, many studies have been devoted to the effects of flow on particles. In particular, [23] investigated the drag and lift forces acting on a cylindrical particle symmetrically located relative to the pipe axis in a Poiseuille flow field. The effects of linear flow on a cylindrical particle were discussed in [24]. The influence of the Magnus force due to particle rotation at the inlet was studied in [25].

The dimensionless drag force per unit cylinder length is calculated using the formula:

$$D = \int_0^{2\pi} \left[-p \cos \theta + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \sin \theta + 2 \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \cos \theta \right] r d\theta = D_p + D_\tau,$$

where $D = D_p + D_\tau$ and D_p is the contribution of pressure forces, and D_τ is the contribution of viscous forces.

The dimensionless lift force per unit cylinder length:

$$L = \int_0^{2\pi} \left[-p \sin \theta + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \cos \theta + 2 \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \sin \theta \right] r d\theta = L_p + L_\tau,$$

where $L = L_p + L_\tau$ and L_p is the contribution of pressure forces, and L_τ is the contribution of viscous forces.

Fig. 1. Streamwise velocity profiles in the inlet section for different cross-sections: $x=0.071; 0.197; 0.496; 0.782$.

The calculations were performed for a dimensionless cylinder radius of 0.05. Table 1 shows the calculated cylinder drag force (DF) at various positions and as a function of the Reynolds number (C is the cylinder center). The highest DF is observed at the beginning of the inlet section near the boundary. With increasing distance from this point, the cylinder center, both vertically and horizontally, exhibits a tendency toward equalizing drag. The rate of decrease in DRF at the initial section ($x = 0.1$) depends on the cylinder center location. Subsequently, particularly at $x = 0.5$ and $x = 1$, DF tends to increase away from the wall. An increase in the Reynolds number contributes to an increase in DF. The contribution of pressure forces to DF is 68-76%.

TABLE I
DRAG FORCE

C	D	Re		C	Re		C	Re	
		100	200		100	200		100	200
(0.1;0.1)	D	57.11	83.89	(0.5;0.1)	14.88	25.23	(1;0.1)	11.08	18.45
	D_p	43.85	68.39		10.57	19.26		7.78	13.90
	D_τ	13.26	15.50		4.31	5397		3.30	4.55
(0.1;0.3)	D	33.49	50.32	(0.5;0.3)	20.39	29.02	(1;0.3)	20.58	29.71
	D_p	23.77	39.09		13.95	21.95		14.04	22.46
	D_τ	9.72	11.23		6.44	7.07		6.54	7.25
(0.1;0.5)	D	32.43	49.04	(0.5;0.5)	19.23	27.34	(1;0.5)	20.79	28.85
	D_p	22.96	38.02		13.11	20.59		14.23	21.80
	D_τ	9.47	11.02		6.12	6.75		6.56	7.05

Table 2 shows the values of the lift force (LF) acting on a particle located at different points in a flat channel. Positive values of the LF indicate that particles located in the initial section of the channel ($0 < x < 1$) tend to move toward the channel axis in the absence of gravity.

With the parameters considered, the greatest flow effect on the cylinder is observed in the initial section of the channel, especially near its walls, which is similar to the distribution of the drag force (DF). At points located near the channel boundary, the magnitude of the lift force reaches almost 50% of the drag force.

As with the drag force, pressure makes a significant contribution to the formation of lift, while the contribution of viscous forces is less significant.

Due to the symmetry of the flow, the lift force acting on a particle located on the channel axis is zero. This condition serves as one of the criteria for the correctness and adequacy of the numerical calculations performed.

TABLE II
LIFT DRAG FORCE

C	L	Re		C	Re		C	Re	
		100	200		100	200		100	200
(0.1;0.1)	L	29.26	29.12	(0.5;0.1)	7.51	10.11	(1;0.1)	5.02	7.17
	L _p	22.95	23.63		5.26	7.12		3.56	5.06
	L _τ	6.31	5.49		2.25	2.99		1.46	2.11
(0.1;0.3)	L	0.77	0.70	(0.5;0.3)	1.69	1.94	(1;0.3)	0.95	1.03
	L _p	0.45	0.45		1.05	1.35		0.54	0.66
	L _τ	0.32	0.25		0.64	0.59		0.41	0.37

Figure 2 shows the longitudinal velocity profiles in various channel cross-sections at Re=100, demonstrating the changing flow structure near the cylinder for different particle positions. The presence of a circular cylinder leads to a significant distortion of the original velocity profile.

The graphs show that without the cylinder, the longitudinal velocity profile has an M-shape with two maxima. However, with the cylinder present, the profile structure changes: the number of local velocity maxima increases near the cylinder. This is due to flow redistribution and the formation of additional acceleration zones near the cylinder's surface.

C. The Nature of Lift in Parabolic Flow

Let's consider the effect of the flow on a particle when a parabolic velocity profile is specified at the channel entrance. This profile corresponds to a steady-state laminar flow of a viscous fluid in the channel and is characterized by a maximum velocity at the channel axis and a decrease as it approaches the walls.

In the absence of a cylindrical particle in the flow, the parabolic longitudinal velocity distribution along the channel is maintained and remains virtually unchanged. This is because the flow is fully developed and is determined only by the boundary conditions at the channel walls.

However, the presence of a cylindrical particle leads to a local disturbance of the flow. The flow, interacting with the particle's surface, is forced to bend around it, causing a redistribution of velocities and a change in the flow structure in its vicinity. As a result, the original longitudinal velocity profile is deformed, and additional velocity and pressure gradients are formed. These

Fig. 2. Longitudinal velocity profiles at the inlet section for different cross-sections: x=0.071; 0.197; 0.496; 0.782, Re=100.

changes have a significant impact on the hydrodynamic forces acting on the particle, particularly the drag and lift forces, the magnitude and direction of which depend on both the flow parameters and the particle's position in the channel.

Numerical calculations were performed to study the influence of the Reynolds number and the particle's position in the channel on the magnitude and direction of the hydrodynamic forces acting on it. The primary focus was on analyzing the lift force (LF) arising from the asymmetry of the velocity and pressure distribution in the flow around the particle.

In the problems considered in the previous sections, a uniform velocity profile was specified at the channel inlet in the range $0 < y < 1$. Under these conditions, it was found that the lift force acting on the particle depends on its position in the channel cross-section. Specifically, LF takes positive values in the lower part of the channel, leading to a displacement of the particle in the direction of the channel axis, while in the upper part of the channel, the lift force is negative. When a parabolic velocity profile is specified at the inlet, the nature of the lift distribution changes significantly. This is due to the fact that a parabolic velocity distribution initially exhibits pronounced non-uniformity in the transverse direction, which alters the flow structure near the particle and the pressure distribution on its surface.

As a result, the magnitude and sign of the lift force acting on the particle depend significantly on both the Reynolds number, which determines the ratio of inertial and viscous forces in the flow, and the particle's position in the channel cross-section. Changing these parameters can result in different modes of particle-flow interaction, manifested by changes in the direction and intensity of the lift force acting on it.

Table 3 lists the coordinates of the cylinder center at which the lift force (LF) acting on the particle vanishes (for the lower part of the channel). These values characterize the particle positions at which the hydrodynamic forces arising in the flow are balanced, and there is no transverse movement of the particle. The value of 0.5 given in the table corresponds to the position of the cylinder's center on the channel axis. Due to the symmetry of the flow, this point is the only point in the cross-section at which the lift force is zero. This particle position can be considered neutral in terms of the action of transverse hydrodynamic forces.

An interval, for example (0.34; 0.35), means that at a Reynolds number $Re=50$, in the channel cross-section $x=0.2$, there exists an additional region $y \in (0.34; 0.35)$, within which is located the point (x, y) , for which the lift force also vanishes. The presence of such an interval indicates the emergence of additional equilibrium positions of the particle in the transverse direction. At low Reynolds numbers ($Re \leq 20$), there are no additional cylinder positions corresponding to zero lift. In this case, the only point where the lift force is zero is the channel axis. As the Reynolds number increases, the flow structure becomes more complex, leading to the emergence of new points where the lift force vanishes.

Furthermore, increasing the Reynolds number shifts these points toward the channel walls. This indicates that at higher Re values, the influence of inertial effects increases, leading to a change in the pressure and velocity distribution near the particle and, consequently, to the formation of additional dynamic equilibrium positions.

TABLE III
CHARACTER OF LIFT FORCE

Reynolds number	Flat pipe cross-section				
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5	1
10	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
20	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
30	0.38;0.39)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
40	(0.30; 0.31)	(0.41;0.42)	0.5	0.5	0.5
50	(0.26;0.27)	(0.34;0.35)	(0.44;0.45)	0.5	0.5
100	(0.18; 0.19)	(0.22;0.23)	0.25;0.26)	(0.31;0.32)	(0.31;0.32)
200	(0.13; 0.14)	(0.15;0.16)	(0.17;0.18)	(0.18;0.19)	(0.18;0.19)

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A numerical study of the interaction of a viscous fluid flow at the inlet section with a cylindrical particle located in a flat channel was conducted for various Reynolds numbers and different particle positions in the channel cross-section. At the inlet section of the channel, ignoring the particle, the formation of an M-shaped velocity profile was observed in the initial cross-sections of the pipe.

It was found that the presence of a cylindrical particle leads to a disturbance of the initial flow velocity profile and its redistribution in the vicinity of the particle. This results in the formation of localized regions of flow acceleration and deceleration, which significantly affects the hydrodynamic forces acting on the particle. It is shown that the nature of the lift distribution depends on the type of inlet velocity profile. With a uniform velocity profile, the lift takes positive values in the lower part of the channel and negative values in the upper part, due to the asymmetry of the velocity and pressure distribution around the particle.

When a parabolic velocity profile is specified, the flow structure in the channel changes, leading to a change in the lift distribution. The magnitude and sign of the lift force depend significantly on both the Reynolds number and the particle's position in the channel cross-section. It was found that at low Reynolds numbers ($Re \leq 20$), the only point in the channel cross-section at which the lift force is zero is the channel axis. As the Reynolds number increases, additional particle positions corresponding to zero lift arise.

It was shown that with increasing Reynolds number, new points at which the lift force vanishes shift toward the channel walls. This indicates an increase in the influence of inertial effects and a more complex flow structure in the vicinity of the particle.

These results provide a deeper understanding of the interactions between particles and the flow in channels and can be used to analyze particle transport and distribution processes in microchannels and various hydrodynamic systems.

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